

Example Data Management Plan – concise version

Investigating biochemical and structural changes to brain white matter in ageing rodents following immune challenge

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

Organisation
ELIXIR-UK

Created by

Jamie
McQueen
id [0000-0001-7172-7504](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7172-7504)

Based on

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I. Data areas and data types

We will collect the following types of quantitative data: confocal imaging, FACS and proteomics. We will also generate associated research records, metadata, protocols, code and other forms of documentation. Based on power calculations and pilot experiments, we estimate that we will generate approximately 12 TB of imaging data, 120 MB of FACS data, and around 18-24 GB of proteomics data.

II. Standards and metadata

Data will be documented to the highest standards throughout the project to enable reproducibility and compliance with BBSRC policy. Imaging data will adopt the REMBI standards to capture all metadata during acquisition and analysis. FACS data will utilise the MIFlowCyt metadata standards and proteomics data will employ the MIAPE standards. These three metadata standards are well-established within the respective fields and are therefore the most appropriate for this study.

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

This study will generate new primary data using an existing mouse model. We will use related datasets from published literature within the field, where possible, for comparison and verification of findings.

IV. Secondary use

Data will be freely available following publication to all interested researchers working within the field. This will allow the wider research community to utilise the datasets for the validation of findings or new purposes.

V. Methods for data sharing

All data will be curated using repository guidance and will include associated metadata as described above. Imaging data will be deposited in BioImage Archive, FACS data will be deposited in FlowRepository, and proteomics data will be deposited in PRIDE. Notes will be included within a data deposit to point to associated data from the project within alternative repositories, and where possible, DOIs for linked data deposits will be included. Data will be

deposited in open-access data repositories and made available at the point of publication in an open-access journal(s), enabling access to any interested parties. The results of the research project will be presented at local and international conferences. We will also engage with the University Communications and Press Office departments to promote research findings via social media or a press release.

VI. Proprietary data

We do not anticipate any delays to data sharing following publication, however, we reserve the right to a restricted and appropriate period of exclusive use if required to protect potential Intellectual Property rights.

VII. Timeframes

We reserve the right to retain unpublished data until sufficient validation has been conducted to allow meaningful and robust analysis. Data will be publicly available at the point of publication in an open-access journal

VIII. Format of the final dataset

Data will be stored in raw formats as standard to prevent data loss. Imaging data will be stored as .czi, FACS as .fcs and proteomics data as .raw and .mzXML. We will also convert proprietary formats to open formats wherever possible (e.g. .czi to .tiff), to ensure maximal reuse by others. Analysed data and project documentation will be in standard formats such as .xls, .doc and .pdf.